

Australian Invasive Species and Pest Genome Partnership

ARDC AUSTRALIAN DATA PARTNERSHIPS PROGRAM
PROJECT FINAL REPORT

Prepared by: Tom Walsh, Rahul Rane, Gunjan Pandey

12/06/2023

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1 PROJECT INFORMATION

INVESTMENT ID	DP727
PROJECT START AND END DATES	Jan 2021 - June 2023
LEAD ORGANISATION	CSIRO
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	ANU Macquarie University University of Melbourne Australian BioCommons Queensland Department of Agriculture and Fisheries South Australian Research and Development Institute
PROJECT CONTACT PERSON	Tom Walsh

1.1 Background

Researchers in all states and territories and across sectors (academia, government and applied research) are incorporating molecular and genomic data into their management, biosecurity preparedness and to assist in developing genetic biocontrol approaches. However, many critical species lack good quality genomes of relevance to Australia or associated functional data and/or pipelines for downstream use and analysis of data assets. Finally, where data is available, most genomes are generated using populations overseas and may not be appropriate for Australian or invasive populations of insects/vertebrates. This project brought together multiple groups with workflows that deliver high quality genomic data assets and analysis pipelines, to resolve this research gap.

Aim: The proposal aimed to generate high quality chromosomal genome assemblies and population resequencing data for Australia's highest priority environment, health and agricultural pests (***as prioritised by Australian stakeholders***).

Deliverable 1- Data assets. High quality chromosomal genome assemblies for Australia's highest priority invasive insect, vertebrate and plant pests. Existing datasets of Lepidoptera and Diptera comprise over 1000 whole genome data sets within Australia, whereas high priority invasive ants or feral cats have none. The project will deliver wet-lab workflows and software pipelines to the wider community along with interactive access to analytical tools (like browsers etc) and computational pipelines.

Deliverable 2 - Data democratisation. Currently Australian relevant pest species genomes and data are hosted in a wide variety of online resources, custom data storage or only publicly available as raw data. We propose to use the community focused Data Access Portal (DAP) from CSIRO to deliver a long-term, version-controlled and continuously curated repository for all raw and processed data, linked to interactive bootable pipelines.

This project is an opportunity to simplify and coordinate pest research in Australia and has the potential to make Australia a world leader in this area.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

During the project's early days, a suggestion was made that the name was too long, so a decision was made to change the name from the Australian Invasive Species and Pest Genome Partnership to the Australian Pest Genome Partnership or APGP. Such was the interest in the concept behind the ARDC funded APGP project that it drove the creation of a larger project, the Applied Genomics Initiative (AGI) within CSIRO. This included funds for retraining staff and a dramatic expansion in the scope to include non-pest and invasive species. APGP now sits as a project within AGI and the broader project aims and deliverables are complementary.

There were two critical aims of the APGP project, incorporated into the core deliverables. These were (1) developing high quality data assets and (2) Increase accessibility of the data.

Aim 1: High quality data assets

Generating high-quality genomic data assets is crucial for advancing research in biology and medicine. With the increasing availability of affordable high-throughput technologies, scientists can now obtain reliable and high-quality sequence information from DNA and RNA molecules. The generation and handling of genomic sequencing data have become routine aspects of many basic science research projects. However, while specialised researchers can deliver these assets, for the vast bulk of researchers/managers/policy makers who would like to apply this data to real world decision making do not have the skills or resources to deliver high quality data assets.

The APGP team, by leveraging expertise and compute resources within and outside CSIRO have been able to deliver a number of high-quality genomic data assets which will enable future research. Each data asset is the start of an "impact journey" and will deliver towards national scale research priorities for many years to come.

Table 1 highlights to data assets created as proposed by the original Australian Invasive Species and Pest Genome Partnership project. Figure 1 describes a rating system developed in this project to describe the

quality of genomes and the potential uses at each quality stage. Appendix I shows the additional data assets created or in progress inspired by the themes developed in the ARDC funded project.

Table 1: Data assets produced/managed through the ARDC project.

Common name	Species	Genome rating*	Data location
Queensland fruit fly	<i>Bactrocera tryoni</i>	****	NCBI Dataset
Lesser Queensland fruit fly	<i>Bactrocera neohumeralis</i>	****	NCBI Dataset
Lepidopteran pests			
	<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	****	Available on request
	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	****	NCBI Dataset
Rodent	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	****	NCBI Dataset
Crown of thorns	<i>Acanthaster planci</i>	****	Submitted to NCBI Dataset
Invasive ants			
Browsing Ant	<i>Lepisiota frauenfeldi</i>	**	Contig/Mitochondrial genome available on request
African black sugar ant	<i>Lepisiota incisa</i>	**	Contig/Mitochondrial genome available on request
Liliuokalani ant	<i>Monomorium liliuokalanii</i>	**	Contig/Mitochondrial genome available on request
Tropical fire ant	<i>Solenopsis geminata</i>	**	
NA	<i>Tetramorium caldarium</i>	**	Contig/Mitochondrial genome available on request
African big-headed ant	<i>Pheidole megacephala</i>	**	Contig/Mitochondrial genome available on request
European grapevine moth	<i>Lobesia botrana</i>	**	Contig/Mitochondrial genome available on request
Yellow crazy ant	<i>Anoplolepis gracilipes</i>	***	Submitted to NCBI Dataset
Mosquitoes	Multiple	*** / ****	CSIRO DAP (embargoed)
African boxthorn	<i>Lycium ferocissimum</i>	****	NCBI Dataset
Annual ryegrass	<i>Lolium rigidum</i>	*****	NCBI Dataset

*Based on the star rating system developed through this project (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Star rating for genome quality and usage

Star	Characteristics	Effort	Application	Your genome?
5*	Chromosomal genome including sex chromosomes	50-100x short read 30 to 40x long read HiC Males and females	Population genetics Gene annotation GWAS, genetic mapping CRISPR target prediction Sex linked genetics Multiomics analyses	Rare
4*	Chromosome scale genome	50-100x short read 30 to 40x long read HiC	Population genetics Gene annotation GWAS, genetic mapping CRISPR target prediction Multiomics analyses	The new standard for genomes
3*	Long, high quality contigs and scaffolds - Less than 5000	50-100x short read 30 to 40x long read	Population genetics Gene annotation GWAS, multiomics	Most genomes
2*	Longer, high quality contigs	50-100x short read coverage	Population genetics Better gene finding	Proto-genome
1*	Many short fragments	< 50x short read assembly	Population genetics Some marker development	eDNA
-	Nothing at all	0	Marker amplification	NA

In summary, generating high-quality genomic data assets involves leveraging affordable high-throughput technologies to obtain reliable sequence information. Visualizing genomic data using specialised techniques and tools helps researchers explore, analyse, and communicate findings effectively. Considering factors such as technical uncertainty, experimental error, and biological variation is essential for creating accurate and informative visual representations. By addressing these challenges, researchers can derive scientific insights and advance our understanding of genomics and its applications in biology and medicine.

Aim 2: Increase accessibility of the data

The vast majority of data assets created during this project are available publicly or will be, subject to publication by collaborators. As the APGP team does not own the material from which much of the genome data was generated, it is difficult for us to guarantee delivery of public data to our timeframe and we must necessarily be constrained by the timelines of our collaborators. However, as highlighted in Table 1 and appendix I and II, much of the data generated is already available or available on request to the team or specific collaborators.

In addition to the reference genomes, Appendix II describes the diversity data assets collated as part of this project.

2 DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1 Achievements against project work packages:

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
1. Stakeholder consultation to evaluate data assets	Individual meetings with all stakeholders were conducted to catalogue assets and requirements by 30th June 2021. Joint stakeholder update was carried out 15th September 2021 for the named stakeholders. However, the number of likely stakeholders has increased significantly due to over-subscription to the projects outcomes and offerings, leading to the need for more wider engagement.	30/06/2021
2. Establish FAIR delivery charter for genomic assets	A FAIR charter has been drafted and adopted. This was following the ARDC FAIR guidelines and has been central to our ethos and operation. See section 8.	30/06/2021
3. Finalise priority lists and delivery tranches	Multiple delivery tranches and priority lists have now been established.	15/09/2021
4. Collation of existing data assets and quality assessment	Existing data assets have been collated after stakeholder consultation (all available on NCBI). Quality assessment standards (details below) have been carried out and decisions have been made regarding output for	30/11/2021

	each species. Website with details now under development.	
5. Establish reference quality metrics for data assets	We have setup a use-case driven standards system for reference genome assets with 1 – 5 stars. This is now the guiding rule for all data assets we engage with in this project.	15/09/2021
6. Create data delivery platforms and websites in collaboration with BioCommons (Apollo + web sites)	Apollo prototyping completed and genomes are now being deployed through Apollo and a collaboration with NCBI's refseq team. Websites with visitor tracking now available through CSIRO (www.appliedgenomics.csiro.au)	30/06/2023
7. Develop new genome assembly software and workflow for new assets or improve existing assets	Novel workflow now completed and being co-developed with CSIRO's Applied Genomics Initiative team to augment the Pyro tool. Galaxy integration was unable to be completed due to financial constraints around dev time.	31/03/2022
8. Outreach and educational activities in collaboration with stakeholders and partners	Extensive collaborative activities have been initiated and/or completed. This includes 3 PhD students, 1 postdoc and has culminated in 2 publications so far on "annual ryegrass" and "fall armyworm" with another 5 in the pipeline.	30/06/2022
9. Create and curate workflows for data management (data access portal, CSIRO)	Workflows have been rigorously tested and data release for each species is now being done through CSIRO's Applied Genomics Initiative, Australian Biocommons and NCBI.	30/03/2022
10. Deploy software deliverables on Galaxy Australia and Github	Pyro-beta is already on github. Stress testing completed, but galaxy integration not feasible in the	30/06/2022

	scope of the project since the task was more complicated and computationally heavy than expected.	
11. Publish the first tranche of data assets and tools	>10+ pest genomes, 2 publications and several trainings have already been completed.	31/03/2022
12. Publish the second tranche of data assets and tools	All data assets not currently being written up by collaborators have been made available.	31/12/2022
13. Publish final tranche of data assets	Data assets as available to date, published or linked to via the AGI website.	30/06/2023
Enable usage tracking on web assets (apollo + landing pages) and CSIRO DAP in the form of visits, downloads, citations and where possible outgoing traffic to Biocommons/ Galaxy Australia servers	Asset access is being co-ordinated through the AGI website, DAP and NCBI as well as citations to the publications. Data tracking in enabled on the AGI website.	30/06/2023
Implement user registration to access the webapollo resource	User registration active, and community adoption now being driven through key opinion leaders attached to every species of concern.	31/12/2022

2.2 Project outputs

This project and the broader AGI have delivered several significant outputs across a number of different areas outlined below and described in Table 1 above. These are both novel outputs that now exist which did not before this project (Table 1, Appendix I and II) but also, and as important, outputs relating to the training and education of staff and collaborators.

Laboratory methodological development

1. Tissue storage and disruption

Tissue for this project is extremely varied with stony coral samples requiring very different handling to those from softer sample types. This has developed expertise in sample handling and preservation that will be useful for the foreseeable future.

2. DNA extraction

This project has implemented new techniques for DNA extraction and trained several staff in CSIRO on high quality DNA and RNA extraction from a wide variety of substrates. These include challenging material such as marine invertebrates to more straightforward samples such as rabbit or mouse tissues.

3. Chromosomally intact DNA extraction

To deliver truly high-quality genome data assets, intact chromosomal DNA must be extracted, a specialised and difficult methodology. Implementation of this approach has required local training of staff and close collaboration with staff at the Biological Resources Facility at the John Curtin School of Medicine at the Australian National University.

4. Extracting the maximum value from poor samples

Some species present practical challenges such as small size or poor sample quality due to the difficulties in collection or one-off samples. Expertise has been developed around quality control of samples and the implementation of novel approaches to use genome amplification tools to increase DNA, sequence output and therefore the quality of the final data asset.

5. Sample tracking

With such a focus on developing reliable data assets we have created a system of sample tracking that we intend to implement within the CSIRO JIRA system. This is project management software that can track samples from receipt through to data asset delivery.

In summary this focus on training and the overall implementation of what has become a large-scale project has led to the development of protocols and procedures that we intend to communicate through best practice recommendations in a proposed manuscript. In addition, the close methodological collaboration with the ANU has led to a successful SIEF bid for novel infrastructure (\$1.4 million PabBio Revio DNA and RNA sequencer).

Informatic expertise development

1. DNA sequencing, QC and genome assembly and diversity datasets

Raw DNA sequencing data can vary enormously in quality and utility so an important part of developing robust, reusable data assets is rigorous and repeatable QC metrics. In this project we established guidelines for QC of the various different data types, Illumina short read sequencing, Oxford nanopore long read sequencing and PacBio HiFi long read sequencing. These QC steps in data analysis have been incorporated into the standard approach to genome assembly.

The Pyro genome assembly pipeline has been published (see below). This approach combines 20 assembly and eight polishing packages, comprising 30 different assembly approaches and up to 48 different polishing approaches in combination. These are available across Illumina short-read, Nanopore and PacBio CLR long-read technologies in one container, complete with data preparation, quality metric calculation and result reporting.

A modified version of this has been deployed within the CSIRO HPC system and has proved so successful in delivering high quality genomes that a number of external collaborators have requested and been granted access, including BPA funded data generation projects.

A number of diversity datasets have been generated for a variety of species (Appendix II) and most of these are currently in the process of analysis by collaborators and will be made public in due course.

2. Data visibility and display

As part of the outputs for this project, staff have developed skills in navigating the various data hosting platforms available, NCBI, Biocommons and the CSIRO data access portal. Upload of quality data assets and managing access is a key output of this project.

Collaborative networks

1. Internal projects

The concept of developing high quality data assets for pests and invasive species has been extremely well received within CSIRO and the original ARDC project inspired the set up of the AGI with an expanded impact area list. This has led to collaborations with all bio-based business units within CSIRO delivering data assets for Agriculture and Food, National Collections and Marine Infrastructure, Health and Biosecurity, Environment and Manufacturing.

2. External projects

The APGP concept has also been very well received by a number of external collaborators with “solving” the data problem an attractive concept for external collaborators. This includes government (DAFF and DCCEEW), industry (RDCs) and academic collaborators.

3. International recognition

Our reference genomes are being taken up by international research groups as well as within Australia and we were recently asked to become a part of the i5k initiative (<https://i5k.nal.usda.gov>), a larger i5k initiative (<http://i5k.github.io>), and the Ag100Pest initiative (<http://i5k.github.io/ag100pest>) as well as the Earth BioGenome Project (<https://www.earthbiogenome.org/affiliated-project-networks>).

Communication

1. Website

A website was constructed to communicate and provide links to the data assets created through the ARDC project and the AGI project <https://appliedgenomics.csiro.au/> and we have recorded visits since May 2022 (Appendix III).

2. Manuscripts published

Pyro: A Comprehensive Pipeline for Eukaryotic Genome Assembly. Dean Southwood, Rahul V. Rane, Siu Fai Lee, John G. Oakeshott, Shoba Ranganathan bioRxiv 2023.04.18.537425; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.04.18.537425>

Thia, J. A., Korhonen, P. K., Young, N. D., Gasser, R. B., Umina, P. A., Yang, Q., Edwards, O., Walsh, T., & Hoffmann, A. A. (2023). The redlegged earth mite draft genome provides new insights into pesticide resistance evolution and demography in its invasive Australian range. *Journal of Evolutionary Biology*, 36, 381–398. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jeb.14144>

Rounding up the annual ryegrass genome: high-quality reference genome of *Lolium rigidum*. Jefferson Paril, Gunjan Pandey, Emma B. Barnett, Rahul V. Rane, Leon Court, Thomas Walsh, Alexandre Fournier-Level. *Frontiers in Genetics* doi: 10.3389/fgene.2022.1012694

3. Manuscripts in progress

A number of further manuscripts (>10) are in progress within CSIRO and many more outside. Unfortunately, as we are not the prime authors we cannot determine the timeline or guarantee the outputs. However, data assets will be made available.

4. Press releases

Two press releases have emerged from this work, which announced the outputs as well as the weed genome for *Lolium rigidum*. These have led to a cumulative of ~100,000 views across multiple media outlets, 5 interviews on radio and print as well as 2 TV interviews.

<https://www.csiro.au/en/news/All/News/2023/April/New-CSIRO-project-to-crack-the-codes-of-Australias-most-invasive-species>

<https://groundcover.grdc.com.au/weeds-pests-diseases/weeds/ground-breaking-research-set-to-establish-better-ryegrass-management-for-aussie-grain-farms>

2.3 Outreach and training activities

ACTIVITY	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	NO. OF PARTICIPANTS	DATE OF ACTIVITY
Workshop	“Impossible without genomics” workshop	~80	15/10/2022
Individual communications with stakeholders	Each data asset generated has a stakeholder and as assets have been delivered	>10	Various

3 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

Data assets have been generated in this project with three broad use cases; environmental, health and agricultural pest monitoring/biocontrol. These assets are subsequently being used by our stakeholders (combination of industry, state and national research/biosecurity agencies and conservation organisations) to inform crucial business decisions, public health, social and environmental policies.

All assets are being delivered in strict compliance with respective gold standards for use-case applications, allowing easier and more confident consumption by translational researchers within and outside partners in this project. The open source publication of data (except select cases) and pipelines is aimed at stimulating collaborative discussion and improvement of bioinformatic pipelines in a local context – and providing clear examples and guidelines for students and educators.

On an infrastructure level, assets and pipelines are mirrored and delivered to researchers and students through public git and Biocommons infrastructure to increase the accessibility and outreach of the same. Visualisation and exploration of assets for pests is being enabled via WebApollo and the CSIRO website.

4 FAIR

4.1 Implementation of FAIR Data Guidelines

FAIR Data Actions

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
1	All data outputs are assigned appropriate PIDs, preferably a DOI	Where public, accession numbers of DOIs (through the CSIRO data portal are available).
2	All data outputs have metadata to enable discovery	Final upload of data assets to biocommons, NCBI and the CSIRO data access portal (DAP) to be completed. Where publication is the aim, data made available as per the journal requirements.
3	All data outputs have a record in Research Data Australia	Yes, via CSIRO DAP
4	All data outputs are registered with relevant discipline-specific discovery aggregators (Recommended , if they exist)	NCBI and Biocommons
5	The persistent identifier for the data output being described is included in the metadata	All data outputs, once uploaded to the relevant repository have a persistent identifier
6	All data outputs are made as openly available as possible; they are only closed where necessary	Several data assets are already on NCBI and CSIRO DAP. These are accessible through FTP's or respective WebDAV API's
7	All data outputs are made available through a repository	
8	All data outputs are available as a download and/or accessible through an open, documented API (where data is not closed)	
9	If the data outputs are not openly available, there is a clear description on the landing page on how to request access to the data outputs and the conditions that need to be met	Contact links for each data asset available on AGI website.
10	The persistent identifier for the data output points to a landing page about the data output, even if the data output is not public (open).	Each species has either a NCBI or DAP accession at time of publication.

11	If the data output is not openly available there is an authorisation and authentication procedure to provide access to the data	Access is via NCBI and CSIRO DAP, however all assets are available upon request
12	The persistent identifier for the data output continues to point to a landing page, even if the data output is no longer available, and there is a policy to maintain these landing pages	Accessions are being linked to NCBI landing pages to avoid individual page maintenance overhead for CSIRO team
13	Data outputs use community-agreed standard data formats (where such agreed formats exist)	All formats are FASTA and community standards
14	Metadata for the data output uses community-agreed standards (where such agreed standards exist)	All meta-data follows NCBI standards
15	Data and metadata use community-agreed vocabularies, data models and ontologies (Recommended , preferably internationally agreed ones where they exist)	All meta-data follows NCBI standards. This is a globally accepted standard
16	Metadata contains persistent identifiers for research objects and entities (people, organisations) linked to the data outputs (including ORCIDs, grantIDs, RAIDs, DOIs, IGSNs)	Each data asset has an independent DOI which will come online by 30 th June 2023.
17	All data outputs are assigned a machine readable licence (preferably CC-BY 4.0)	All open data are CC-BY 4.0
18	The licence information is available in a machine readable form on the landing page that the persistent identifier (for the data output) refers to	NCBI or CSIRO DAP have licence information readily available
19	There is a citation statement for the data output on the landing page that the persistent identifier refers to	Will be made fully available by 30 th June 2023 where currently unavailable

20	Provenance information on the data output is attached alongside the data (Recommended)	As part of the publication process, outputs and data sets will reference each other.
21	Relevant discipline-specific metadata to enable reuse is captured and presented alongside the data output following research community best practice (Recommended)	To be done as part of the publication process.

5 PROJECT IMPACT

The ARDC and the Government wish to demonstrate the impact on researchers, industry and the general public of the NCRIS investment.

5.1 Communications and Engagement

ACTIVITY	DETAILS	LINK TO MATERIALS
Creation of website	A website describing the AGI and APGP specifically was created within the CSIRO system	https://appliedgenomics.csiro.au/
Manuscripts	3 published, many more in progress	See outputs above.
Biocommons webapollo resources		https://www.biocommons.org.au/apollo

5.2 Research Outcomes Planning

ACTIVITY	DETAILS
Establishment of a monitoring framework (for project outcomes and impacts)	Usage and download statistics are and will continue to be collected.
Inputs from research users in design of the infrastructure	As both research users and generators, we have had extensive informal inputs into the structure.
Partnerships with research translation specialists	Discussions with CSIRO, ARDC and Biocommons comms officers is ongoing.
Establishment of policies, systems and workflows to track uptake (of project outcomes)	Manuscripts, data downloads to be monitored.
Establishment of data delivery frameworks and a community of practice (to drive uptake)	Demonstrated as part of the workshop and the planned workshop.

6 LESSONS LEARNED

6.1 What Went Well?

The successful delivery of a genomics data project requires careful planning, collaboration, and adherence to best practices in genomics research and data management. By following a systematic approach and leveraging available resources, this project has achieved its objectives and contributed to advancements in scientific knowledge and developed data assets for Australia.

This project enabled us to demonstrate and develop skills and expertise that have delivered into a large scale expansion of the scope of the original project. One of the most useful lessons from this project in terms of delivering a clear message with established guidelines for delivery as well as a focus on assets rather than publications.

A few simple themes/needs have emerged as we conducted 100+ conversations with collaborators:

“Data is easy, analysis is hard”

Australian scientists do not have equitable access to data, and a centralised focused approach allowed us to deliver low-cost and rapid access to data generation, making it easy. The analysis however still remains hard due to species specific challenges and scale, which is where future work would reside.

“Digital transformation of biology”

Making the analysis as streamlined as we have been able to in the APGP and AGI projects, has critically enabled digital transformation in research areas where it was seen as being highly challenging earlier.

“Researchers do not want to DO genomics; they want to USE genomics”

There is a significant need for scientists to use genomics, rather than learn the coding to do things themselves.

In combination, we also developed metrics for how to measure outputs and what the various levels could be used for. In particular the star rating for genomics assets developed in this project at the outset delivered an easy to understand series of metrics with potential outputs and use cases.

6.2 What Could be Improved?

This project began as a relatively small-scale exercise in generating new data, making existing data available and ensuring data was available for reuse and broadly to researchers. What we did not anticipate was the appetite, in CSIRO, in the wider academic world, in industry, government and increasingly internationally for the type of work that we have done in this project.

The increase in volume led to some delays in some of the project deliverables around data availability however, we anticipate a full and comprehensive delivery of data and data assets in relation to this project over the coming months and we look forward to reporting back on these as we continue to develop from the excellent start that we have made.

We also identified a major weakness in making these data assets usable in that annotation is a major bottle neck. Australian Biocommons have implemented a pipeline but what was missing in this project was a focus on developing annotation data for genome resources. In order to overcome this limitation we established a good relationship with the annotation group at NCBI but even then, annotation can take up to six months.

Finally, a vast majority of the scientists and decision makers we spoke to as part of APGP and the AGI project indicated a need for a plug and play analytical platform, citing hesitation to adopt programming or even easy-to-use platforms such as Galaxy. This project delivered such a proof of concept for genome

assemblies, and the demand has only grown after this. What could be done better in the future is a more systematic and larger-scale enablement piece, which will deliver highly standardised and well supported end-to-end solutions that are plug and play with fixed outputs. This will cover the vast majority of the scientific needs of the community.

Appendix I: Reference genome data assets generated or underway

Impact area: **Agriculture and Biosecurity**

Species	Common name	Class	Output domain	Assembly status	Assembly level	Contact
<i>Calliphora hilli</i>	Blow fly	Insecta	Agriculture	Assembled	Contig	Angela McGaughran
<i>Calliphora stygia</i>	Brown blowfly	Insecta	Agriculture	Assembled	Contig	Angela McGaughran
<i>Calliphora vicina</i>	Blue bottle fly	Insecta	Agriculture	Assembled	Contig	Angela McGaughran
<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Cotton bollworm	Insecta	Agriculture	Assembled	Scaffold	AGI Team
<i>Helicoverpa punctigera</i>	Australian bollworm	Insecta	Agriculture	Assembled	Scaffold	AGI Team
<i>Creontiades dilutus</i>	Green mirid	Insecta	Agriculture	Coming soon	Scaffold	AGI Team
<i>Dermolepida albohirtum</i>	Cane beetle	Insecta	Agriculture	Coming soon	Scaffold	AGI Team
<i>Kuschelorrhynchus macadamiae</i>	Macadamia seed weevil	Insecta	Agriculture	Coming soon	Scaffold	Hermes E. Garcia
<i>Myzus persicae</i>	Green peach aphid	Insecta	Agriculture	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Nysius vinitor</i>	Rutherglen Bug	Insecta	Agriculture	Coming soon	Scaffold	James Hereward
<i>Onthophagus vacca</i>	Dung beetle	Insecta	Agriculture	Coming soon	Scaffold	Matt Morgan
<i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i>	Cotton mealybug	Insecta	Agriculture	Coming soon	Contig	Jamie Hopkinson
<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	Tobacco cutworm	Insecta	Agriculture	Coming soon	Scaffold	AGI Team
<i>Rhinella marina</i>	Canetoad	Amphibia	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Scaffold	Lee Rollins
<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	Wild radish	Brassicaceae	Biosecurity	Assembled	Chromosome	Kumaran Nagalingam
<i>Bactrocera dorsalis</i>	Oriental fruit fly	Insecta	Biosecurity	Assembled	Scaffold	Ronald Lee

<i>Bactrocera frauenfeldi</i>	Mango fruit fly	Insecta	Biosecurity	Assembled	Scaffold	Ronald Lee
<i>Bactrocera kraussi</i>	Krauss's fruit fly	Insecta	Biosecurity	Assembled	Scaffold	Ronald Lee
<i>Bactrocera neohumeralis</i>	Lesser Queensland fruit fly	Insecta	Biosecurity	Assembled	Chromosome	Ronald Lee
<i>Bactrocera pallida</i>		Insecta	Biosecurity	Assembled	Scaffold	Ronald Lee
<i>Bactrocera tryoni</i>	Queensland fruit fly	Insecta	Biosecurity	Assembled	Chromosome	Ronald Lee
<i>Helicoverpa zea</i>	Corn earworm	Insecta	Biosecurity	Assembled	Scaffold	AGI Team
<i>Bactrocera aquilonis</i>	Northern Territory fruit fly	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Scaffold	Ronald Lee
<i>Bactrocera jarvisi</i>	Jarvis' fruit fly	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Chromosome	Ronald Lee
<i>Brachymyrmex obscurior</i>	Ant	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Contig	Ben Hoffmann
<i>Ceratitis capitata</i>	Mediterranean fruit fly	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Conopomorpha cramerella</i>	Cocoa pod borer	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Scaffold	Mars
<i>Diuraphis noxia</i>	Russian wheat aphid	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Lepisiota frauenfeldi</i>	Browsing Ant	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Contig	Ben Hoffmann
<i>Lepisiota incisa</i>	African black sugar ant	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Contig	Ben Hoffmann
<i>Lobesia botrana</i>	European grapevine moth	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Scaffold	Wee Tek-Tay
<i>Monomorium liliuokalanii</i>	Liliuokalani ant	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Contig	Ben Hoffmann
<i>Oryctes rhinoceros</i>	Coconut rhinoceros beetle	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Scaffold	Wee Tek-Tay
<i>Pheidole megacephala</i>	African big-headed ant	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Contig	Ben Hoffmann
<i>Solenopsis geminata</i>	Tropical fire ant	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Contig	Ben Hoffmann
<i>Tetramorium caldarium</i>	Ant	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Contig	Ben Hoffmann

<i>Trogoderma granarium</i>	Khapra beetle	Insecta	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Scaffold	AGI Team
<i>Bactrocera albistrigata</i>	White striped fruit fly	Insecta	Biosecurity	Data generation	Contig	Ronald Lee
<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Silverleaf whitefly	Insecta	Biosecurity	Data generation	Contig	AGI team
<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Fall armyworm	Insecta	Biosecurity	Public – refseq	Chromosome	AGI Team
<i>Gastrolobium bilobum</i>	Heart-leaved poison	Magnoliopsida	Biosecurity	Data generation	Scaffold	CSIRO
<i>Gastrolobium calycinum</i>	York Road Poison	Magnoliopsida	Biosecurity	Data generation	Scaffold	CSIRO
<i>Gastrolobium parviflorum</i>	Box poison	Magnoliopsida	Biosecurity	Data generation	Scaffold	CSIRO
<i>Gastrolobium spinosum</i>	Prickly poison	Magnoliopsida	Biosecurity	Data generation	Scaffold	CSIRO
<i>Gastrolobium villosum</i>	Crinkle-leaved Poison	Magnoliopsida	Biosecurity	Data generation	Scaffold	CSIRO
<i>Felis catus</i>	Domestic cat	Mammalia	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	European rabbit	Mammalia	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Contig	Tanja Strive
<i>Rattus rattus</i>	House rat	Mammalia	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Chromosome	AGI Team
<i>Sus scrofa</i>	Feral pig	Mammalia	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>	Red fox	Mammalia	Biosecurity	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Lolium rigidum</i>	Annual grass	Poaceae	Biosecurity	Public – refseq	Chromosome	Alexandre Fournier-Level
<i>Lycium ferocissimum</i>	African boxthorn	Solanaceae	Biosecurity	Assembled	Chromosome	Kumaran Nagalingam

Impact area: **Circular economy**

Species	Common name	Class	Output domain	Assembly status	Assembly level	Contact
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<i>Galleria mellonella</i>	Greater wax moth	Insecta	Circular economy	Assembled	Scaffold	Gene Wijffels
<i>Hermetia illucens</i>	Black soldier fly	Insecta	Circular economy	Coming soon	Scaffold	AGI Team
<i>Schistorhinotermes sp.</i>	Termite	Insecta	Circular economy	Coming soon	Scaffold	Gene Wijffels
<i>Tenebrio molitor</i>	Mealworm	Insecta	Circular economy	Coming soon	Scaffold	Gene Wijffels
<i>Tineola bisselliella</i>	Common clothes moth	Insecta	Circular economy	Coming soon	Scaffold	AGI Team
<i>Zophobas morio</i>	Superworm larvae	Insecta	Circular economy	Data generation	Scaffold	Chris Rinke

Impact area: Conservation

Species	Common name	Class	Output domain	Assembly status	Assembly level	Contact
<i>Bidyanus bidyanus</i>	Silver perch	Actinopterygii	Conservation	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Craterocephalus fluviatilis</i>	Murray hardyhead	Actinopterygii	Conservation	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Craterocephalus stercusmuscarum fulvus</i>	Unspecked hardyhead	Actinopterygii	Conservation	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Galaxias fuscus</i>	Barred galaxias	Actinopterygii	Conservation	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Maccullochella macquariensis</i>	Trout cod	Actinopterygii	Conservation	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Macquaria australasica</i>	Macquarie perch	Actinopterygii	Conservation	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Mogurnda adspersa</i>	Southern purple-spotted gudgeon	Actinopterygii	Conservation	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Nannoperca australis</i>	Southern pygmy perch	Actinopterygii	Conservation	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Nannoperca obscura</i>	Yarra pygmy perch	Actinopterygii	Conservation	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team

<i>Nannoperca oxleyana</i>	Oxleyan pygmy perch	Actinopterygii	Conservation	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Prototroctes maraena</i>	Australian grayling	Actinopterygii	Conservation	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Pseudaphritis urvillii</i>	Congolli	Actinopterygii	Conservation	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Tandanus tandanus</i>	Eel-tailed catfish	Actinopterygii	Conservation	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Leucochrysum albicans</i>	Hoary sunray	Asteraceae	Conservation	Assembled	Scaffold	Alexander Schmidt-Lebuhn
<i>Pezoporus wallicus</i>	Eastern Ground Parrot	Aves	Conservation	Coming soon	Chromosome	Leo Joseph
<i>Phoracantha sp Male</i>	Longicorn Beetle	Insecta	Conservation	Coming soon	Scaffold	Matthew Brookhouse
<i>Stylophora pistillata</i>	Hood coral	Insecta	Conservation	Coming soon	Scaffold	UQ/AIMS
<i>Dasyuroides byrnei</i>	Marsupial rat	Mammalia	Conservation	Coming soon	Scaffold	Denis-Bauer
<i>Thelymitra variegata</i>	Queen of Sheba	Orchidaceae	Conservation	Data generation	Scaffold	Katharina Schulte
<i>Tasmania lanceolata</i>	Tasmanian pepperberry	Winteraceae	Conservation	Coming soon	Scaffold	Alexandre Fournier-Level

Impact area: Environment

Species	Common name	Class	Output domain	Assembly status	Assembly level	Contact
<i>Ambassis agassizii</i>	Olive Perchlet		Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig AGI Team
<i>Carassius auratus</i>	Gold fish		Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig AGI Team

<i>Centroberyx affinis</i>	Redfish	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Centroberyx gerrardi</i>	Bight Redfish	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Craterocephalus amniculus</i>	Darling River hardyhead	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	European carp	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Gadopsis bispinosus</i>	Two-spined blackfish	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Gadopsis marmoratus</i>	Southern river blackfish	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Gadopsis marmoratus</i>	Northern river blackfish	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Galaxias arcanus</i>	Riffle galaxias	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Galaxias brevipinnis</i>	Climbing galaxias	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Galaxias olidus</i>	Mountain galaxias	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Galaxias oliros</i>	Obscure galaxias	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Galaxias rostratus</i>	Flathead galaxias	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Gambusia holbrooki</i>	Eastern gambusia	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Geotria australis</i>	Pouched lamprey	Hyperoartia	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Hypseleotris</i> sp.	Lake's carp gudgeon	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Hypseleotris klunzingeri</i>	Western carp gudgeon	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team

<i>Hypseleotris</i> sp.	Murray-Darling carp gudgeon	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Hypseleotris</i> sp.	Midgley's carp gudgeon	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Leiopotherapon unicolor</i>	Spangled perch	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Maccullochella peelii peelii</i>	Murray cod	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Macquaria ambigua</i>	Golden perch	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Melanotaenia fluviatilis</i>	Murray river rainbowfish	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Melanotaenia splendida tatei</i>	Desert rainbowfish	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Misgurnus anguillicaudatus</i>	Oriental weatherloach	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Monoplex parthenopeus</i>	Giant triton	Gastropoda	Environment	Coming soon	Scaffold	Cherie Motti
<i>Mordacia mordax</i>	Short headed lamprey	Hyperoartia	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Mordacia praecox</i>	Non-parasitic lamprey	Hyperoartia	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Musca vetustissima</i>	Australian bush fly	Insecta	Environment	Data generation	Scaffold	Juan David Lobarton
<i>Nematalosa erebi</i>	Bony herring	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Neosilurus hyrtlii</i>	Hyrtl's tandan	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Rainbow trout	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team

<i>Perca fluviatilis</i>	European perch	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Philypnodon grandiceps</i>	Flathead gudgeon	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Philypnodon macrostomus</i>	Dwarf flathead gudgeon	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Pocillopora verrucosa</i>	Cauliflower coral	Hexacorallia	Environment	Coming soon	Scaffold	UQ/AIMS
<i>Retropinna semoni</i>	Australian smelt	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Saccostrea cucullata</i>	Oyster	Bivalvia	Environment	Data generation	Scaffold	Sharon Hook
<i>Saccostrea echinate</i>	Oyster	Bivalvia	Environment	Data generation	Scaffold	Sharon Hook
<i>Saccostrea glomerata</i>	Sydney rock oyster	Bivalvia	Environment	Data generation	Scaffold	Sharon Hook
<i>Salmo trutta</i>	Brown trout	Actinopterygii	Environment	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Ylistrum balloti</i>	Ballot's saucer scallop	Bivalvia	Environment	Data generation	Scaffold	Sharon Hook

Impact area: **Health**

Species	Common name	Class	Output domain	Assembly status	Assembly level	Contact	
<i>Aedes burpengaryensis</i>	Mosquito		Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Aedes candidoscutellum</i>	Mosquito		Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Aedes eidsvoldensis</i>	Mosquito		Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team

<i>Aedes flavifrons</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Aedes imperfectus</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Aedes keeferi</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Aedes kochi</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Aedes palmarum</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Aedes quinquelineatus</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Aedes rubrithorax</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Aedes sp. Marks #51</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Aedes sp. Marks #85</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Aedes wasselli</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Anopheles annulipes</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Anopheles colledgei</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Anopheles corethroides</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Anopheles pseudostigmaticus</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Coquillettidia xanthogaster</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Culex douglasi</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Culex insequens</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Culex pseudomelanoconia</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Culiseta frenchii</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Pediculus humanus capitis</i>	Head louse	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team

<i>Tripteroides apicotriangulatus</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Tripteroides atripes</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Tripteroides punctolateralis</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Verrallina lineata</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Coming soon	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Aedes camptorhynchus</i>	Southern saltmarsh mosquito	Insecta	Health	Data generation	Scaffold	AGI Team
<i>Aedes notoscriptus</i>	Australian backyard mosquito	Insecta	Health	Data generation	Scaffold	AGI Team
<i>Aedes vigilax</i>	Saltmarsh mosquito	Insecta	Health	Data generation	Scaffold	AGI Team
<i>Anopheles farauti</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Data generation	Contig	Nigel Beebe
<i>Anopheles stigmaticus</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	Data generation	Contig	AGI Team
<i>Anoplolepis gracilipes</i>	Yellow Crazy Ant	Insecta	Health	Data generation	Contig	Ben Hoffmann
<i>Culex annulirostris</i>	Common banded mosquito	Insecta	Health	Data generation	Chromosome	AGI Team

Appendix II: Diversity data assets

*indicates species identified as part of the ARDC funded project.

Species	Common name	Class	Output domain	no.	Contact	Output location
<i>Acropora cytherea</i>	stony coral	Anthozoa	Conservation	9	AGI team	NCBI/DAP
<i>Acropora hyacinthus</i>	stony coral	Anthozoa	Conservation	964	AGI team	NCBI/DAP
<i>Acropora millepora</i>	stony coral	Anthozoa	Conservation	57	AGI team	NCBI/DAP
<i>Acropora tenuis</i>	stony coral	Anthozoa	Conservation	10	AGI team	NCBI/DAP
<i>Pocillopora acuta</i>	Cauliflower coral	Anthozoa	Conservation	6	AGI team	NCBI/DAP
<i>Pocillopora damicornis</i>	Cauliflower coral	Anthozoa	Conservation	15	AGI team	NCBI/DAP
<i>Pocillopora eydouxi</i>	Cauliflower coral	Anthozoa	Conservation	3	AGI team	NCBI/DAP
<i>Pocillopora verrucosa</i>	Cauliflower coral	Anthozoa	Conservation	37	AGI team	NCBI/DAP
<i>Stylophora pistillata</i>	Hood coral	Anthozoa	Conservation	147	AGI team	NCBI/DAP
* <i>Mus musculus</i>	Mice	Mammalia	Biosecurity	80	AGI team	Embargo
<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	Rabbit	Mammalia	Biosecurity	402	Tanja Strive	Embargo
<i>Apis mellifera</i>	Honey Bee	Insecta	Conservation	48	Angel Popa	Embargo for publication
* <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Cotton bollworm	Insecta	Biosecurity	>400	AGI team	NCBI/DAP
* <i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Fall armyworm	Insecta	Biosecurity	355	AGI team	NCBI/DAP
<i>Carukia barnesi</i>	Irukandji jellyfish	Cubozoa	Health	52	Pascal Craw	NCBI/DAP
* <i>Anopheles farauti</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Health	40	AGI team	Embargo
* <i>Solenopsis geminata</i>	Tropical fire ant	Insecta	Biosecurity	96	AGI team	DAP
<i>Culex annulirostris</i>	Mosquito	Insecta	Biosecurity	28	AGI team	Embargo
* <i>Bactrocera tryoni</i>	Queensland fruit fly	Insecta	Biosecurity	50	Ronald Lee	NCBI/DAP

<i>*Bactrocera neohumeralis</i>	Lesser Queensland fruit fly	Insecta	Biosecurity	50	Ronald Lee	NCBI/DAP	
<i>Lobesia botrana</i>	European grapevine moth	Insecta	Biosecurity	1	Wee Tek-Tay	DAP	
<i>Lolium rigidum</i>	Annual ryegrass	Planta	Environment/Biosecurity	1	Alexandre Fournier-level	NCBI/DAP	

Appendix III: Website Visitor statistics

2022

2023

Total stats:

